

Antioxidant Potential of Olive Pulp Phenolic Extracts and Their Protective Effect against Lipid Peroxidation

Fatiha Abdellah

Laboratory of Research on Local Animal Products at Ibn Khaldoun University, Tiaret- Algeria

Abstract

Olive (*Olea europaea* L.) is one of the most widely used medicinal plants in traditional medicine. It is rich in bioactive compounds with beneficial properties. Extracts from its fruits contain various constituents, including polyphenols and flavonoids, which are known for their strong antioxidant activity. This study was conducted to evaluate the antioxidant activity of phenolic extracts from olive pulp (*Olea europaea* L.) of the Chemlal and Sigoise varieties using three standard assays: reducing power, DPPH radical scavenging, and hydrogen peroxide neutralization. Lipid peroxidation was assessed by measuring thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS). Quantitative analysis revealed that olive pulp is rich in polyphenols and flavonoids, although flavonoid content was lower compared to polyphenols. The results showed that the phenolic extracts of olive pulp exhibited strong DPPH• scavenging activity, with IC₅₀ values of 158.1 ± 2.57 µg/mL for olive pulp extract from Chemlal variety and 174.11 ± 2.20 µg/mL for Sigoise olive pulp extract. This antioxidant potential was further supported by the reducing power assay, which showed EC₅₀ values of 1301 ± 57.79 µg/mL and 1468.99 ± 0.94 µg/mL for the Chemlal and Sigoise varieties, respectively. In addition, the extracts efficiently neutralized hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), with IC₅₀ values of 117.32 ± 2.36 µg/mL for Chemlal variety and 493.29 ± 1.3 µg/mL for Sigoise variety. Moreover, both extracts demonstrated a significant protective effect against lipid peroxidation. Overall, the findings highlight the richness of olive pulp phenolic extracts in bioactive compounds with strong antioxidant activity, suggesting their potential application as natural antioxidants in the food and pharmaceutical industries.

Key words: *Olea europaea* L., Polyphenols, Antioxidant activity, Lipid Peroxidation, Protective effect.

1. INTRODUCTION

Reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as superoxide radicals, hydrogen peroxide, and hydroxyl radicals, are natural byproducts of cellular metabolism. At physiological levels, ROS play essential roles in various biological processes. However, when their production exceeds the body's antioxidant defenses, oxidative stress arises, leading to damage of essential biomolecules such as DNA, proteins, and lipids. This imbalance has been strongly associated with the onset of several chronic conditions, including cardiovascular diseases, atherosclerosis, and hypertension [1]. Over the past few decades, the field of nutrition has completely changed. It has evolved into a discipline not only interested in the essential nutrients for survival and growth, but also in the bioactive compounds found in the human diet that can optimize body function and overall health. Bioactive molecules are substances that are not essential for the maintenance of bodily functions, but which can promote health and / or prevent the onset of some diseases. Several epidemiological studies have showed that following a plant-based diet rich in bioactive molecules such as polyphenols offers protection against the development of cancers, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes and osteoporosis [2]. *Olea europaea* is one of the most widely used medicinal plants in traditional medicine. This plant is rich in natural compounds with beneficial effects. Some bioactive compounds identified in the extracts of its fruits, such as phenolic compounds and flavonoids, are endowed with extremely significant antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity. In Algeria *Olea europaea* species occupies as much as 2.3% of the total cultivated surface, but this important olive resources are not valorized [3]. The main Objective of this study is the *in vitro* evaluation of the antioxidant activity of phenolic extracts from olive pulp (*Olea europaea* L.) and their protective effect against lipid peroxidation.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Plant material

The two olive pulp varieties, Chemlal and Sigoise, used in this study were collected from different regions of Algeria. Chemlal olive pulp was obtained from the TiziOuzou region (36°42'42" N, 4°02'45" E), while Sigoise olive pulp was collected from the Sig region (35°32'00" N, 0°11'00" W; altitude 56 m). The samples were harvested in December 2023, washed, dried at 50 °C, and stored in light-protected glass bottles until further use.

2.2. Extraction of phenolic compounds

Ten grams of dried olive pulp were macerated in 100 ml of 70% (v/v) aqueous ethanol at room temperature for 24 hours. The obtained extract was then delipidated using hexane, after which the alcoholic phase was evaporated under reduced pressure and low temperature conditions.

2.3. Total phenolic content

The total phenolic content of the tested extracts was evaluated spectrophotometrically using the Folin-Ciocalteu method as described by Singleton et al. [4]. A 200 µL volume of olive pulp extract solutions at different concentrations (0.5–4 mg/mL) was mixed with 500 µL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (10%) and allowed to react for 5 minutes. Subsequently, 1500 µL of sodium carbonate solution (10%) was added. The mixtures were then incubated at room temperature in the dark for 30 minutes, after which absorbance was measured at 765 nm. A calibration curve was prepared using gallic acid standards in the concentration range of 3.125×10^{-3} to 5×10^{-2} mg/mL. The total phenolic content was expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents per gram of dried extract (mg GAE/g).

2.4. Total flavonoid content (TFC)

The total flavonoid content was determined following the method of Quettier et al. [5]. Olive extract solutions at various concentrations (0.5–4 mg/mL) were mixed with an equal volume (1 mL) of 2% aluminum chloride solution. The mixtures were incubated in the dark for 30 minutes, after which their absorbance was recorded at 430 nm. A calibration curve was constructed using quercetin standards within the concentration range of 3.0×10^{-4} to 4.0×10^{-3} mg/mL. Results were expressed as milligrams of quercetin equivalents per gram of dried extract (mg QE/g). All measurements were performed in triplicate.

2.5. Antioxidant activity of the studied extracts

2.5.1. Ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) Test

The ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) of the tested extracts was determined according to the method of Yen and Duh [6], with minor modifications. Briefly, 2.5 mL of each extract solution (31.25–500 µg/mL) was combined with 2.5 mL of potassium ferricyanide (1%) and 2.5 mL of phosphate buffer (0.2 M, pH 6.6), then incubated at 50 °C for 20 min. Afterward, 2.5 mL of trichloroacetic acid (10%) was added, and the mixtures were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min. An aliquot of 1 mL from the supernatant was subsequently mixed with 1 mL of distilled water and 0.5 mL of ferric chloride (0.1%). Ascorbic acid and gallic acid served as reference antioxidants. The increase in absorbance indicated greater reducing activity of the samples. The Results were expressed as the effective concentration (EC₅₀), defined as the extract concentration required achieving an absorbance of 0.5 at 700 nm. Lower EC₅₀ values reflected stronger reducing power.

2.5.2. Free radical scavenging activity (DPPH) Test

The free radical scavenging capacity of the extracts was evaluated using the DPPH assay, following the method of Tien et al. [7] with slight modifications. In brief, 1.5 mL of each sample solution (0.015–1 mg/mL) was mixed with 1.5 mL of 0.2 mMethanolic DPPH solution. The mixtures were incubated at 25 °C for 30 min, and the absorbance was measured at 517 nm (sample). A control was prepared in the same manner without the test material, and its absorbance was recorded as the blank. The radical scavenging activity of each sample was expressed as the percentage of inhibition, calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = 100 \times \frac{A(\text{blank}) - A(\text{sample})}{A(\text{blank})}$$

The antioxidant potential of each phenolic extract was expressed as the IC₅₀ value, corresponding to the concentration necessary to reduce the initial DPPH level by 50%. Ascorbic acid and gallic acid were used as reference standards, and all experiments were conducted in triplicate.

2.5.3. Test of hydrogen peroxide scavenging capacity

The hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity of the studied extracts was evaluated using the method of Kumar et al. [8]. A 40 mM hydrogen peroxide solution was prepared in phosphate buffer (0.1 M, pH 7.4). Then, 2 mL of each extract solution at varying concentrations (0.06–0.5 mg/mL in 70% ethanol) was mixed with 1.2 mL of the hydrogen peroxide solution. After 10 min, the absorbance was measured at 230 nm against a blank consisting of phosphate buffer without hydrogen peroxide. The scavenging efficiency of the extracts and reference standards was expressed as a percentage, calculated according to the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Scavenged } [\text{H}_2\text{O}_2] = 100 \times \frac{\text{AC} - \text{AS}}{\text{AC}}$$

Where

AC represents the absorbance of the control

AS represents the absorbance in the presence of phenolic extracts or reference compounds.

The hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity of the extracts was expressed as the IC₅₀ value, defined as the extract concentration needed to reduce the initial H₂O₂ level by 50%. Ascorbic acid and gallic acid served as standard antioxidants, and all assays were carried out in triplicate.

2.6. Anti-lipid peroxidation activity

2.6.1. Preparation of liver homogenate

Livers were isolated from three healthy albino Wistar rats, and a 10% (w/v) homogenate was prepared in phosphate buffer (0.1 M, pH 7.4) containing 0.15 M KCl, using a homogenizer maintained at 4 °C. The homogenate was then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min, and the resulting supernatant was used for the experiments [9].

2.6.2. Lipid Peroxidation and thiobarbituric acid reactions

The protective effect of the tested extracts against lipid peroxidation was assessed following the method of Gupta and Sharma [10]. Briefly, 580 μL of phosphate buffer (0.1 M, pH 7.4) was mixed with 200 μL of extract (or standard) and 200 μL of liver homogenate. Subsequently, 20 μL of ferric chloride (100 mM, with 0.5% H₂O₂ prepared in phosphate buffer, 0.1 M, pH 7.4) was added, and the mixture was incubated in a shaking water bath at 37 °C for 1 h. Malondialdehyde (MDA) levels were determined. For this, 800 μL of thiobarbituric acid (TBA, 0.375% w/v) was added to 200 μL of the reaction mixture, shaken for 2 min, and incubated at 100 °C for 10 min. During this step, MDA was released by acid hydrolysis and reacted with TBA to form a pink MDA–TBA complex. The reaction was stopped by cooling on ice, and the complex was extracted with 2 mL of 1-butanol for 2 min. After centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C, the supernatant was collected and the absorbance of the chromogen was measured at 532 nm. MDA concentration in tissue samples was calculated from a standard calibration curve, and the percentage of inhibition was determined using the following formula:

$$\text{MDA } (\%) = 100 \times \frac{C_0 - C_1}{C_0}$$

Where C₀ is the MDA concentration without protection and C₁ is the MDA concentration with protection.

2.7. Statistical analysis

All experiments were conducted in triplicate, and the results are expressed as mean values \pm standard deviation. Statistical analysis was performed using Statistica software (version 6.1, StatSoft, Tulsa, UK). Mean comparisons were carried out by one-way ANOVA, followed by Tukey's post hoc test, with significance set at $P < 0.05$.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Extraction yield, phenolic and flavonoids contents

The extraction yield, polyphenols and flavonoids contents of olive pulp extracts are indicated in the following table:

Table 1. Extraction yield, polyphenols and flavonoids contents of olive pulp extracts

Parameter Extract	Extraction yield (%)	Polyphenol content (mg GAE/g of extract)	Flavonoid content (mgQE/g of extract)
Phenolic extract of olive pulp from Chemlal variety	18.70\pm0.50^a	48.46\pm0.36^c	35.65\pm1.19^e
Phenolic extract of olive pulp from Sigoise variety	25.01\pm1.02^b	43.22\pm0.098^d	27.69\pm0.68^f

The values followed by different letters indicate significant differences by ANOVA post hoc LSD Tukey test

$p < 0.05$

3.1.1. Extraction yield

The obtained results indicated that the yield of polyphenols extraction from the olive pulp of the Sigoise variety was significantly higher ($25.01 \pm 1.02\%$) compared to that of the Chemlal variety ($18.70 \pm 0.50\%$). Previous scientific studies have reported that polyphenols extraction yields from olive pulp vary between 2% and 30%. The values obtained in the present study are consistent with those reported in the literature. These yields can vary depending on several factors, including the extraction method, the quality of the olive pulp, the type of solvent, extraction time, temperature, solvent-to-sample ratio, and the specific polyphenols targeted. Moreover, extraction efficiency is influenced by the solubility and stability of the phenolic compounds.

3.1.2. Polyphenols and flavonoids contents

Polyphenols and flavonoids are two major groups of bioactive compounds commonly found in olive pulp extracts. According to the obtained results, it appears that the phenolic extract of olive pulp from the Chemlal variety is particularly rich in polyphenols (48.46 ± 0.36 mg GAE/g of extract) and flavonoids (35.65 ± 1.19 mg QE/g of extract) compared to that of the Sigoise variety. However, we found that the flavonoids content was relatively low compared with the polyphenols content. Polyphenols represent a large class of chemical compounds that are abundant in plant-based foods, including olives. Olive pulp extracts typically contain various polyphenols, such as hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol, oleuropein, and their derivatives. Among these, hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol are considered the main phenolic compounds in olives and olive-derived products, while oleuropein is particularly abundant in unripe fruits. They are characterized by the presence of multiple phenolic rings and have been widely studied for their potential health benefits. Flavonoids, a subgroup of polyphenols, are known for their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. They are present in a wide range of fruits, vegetables, and plant-based products, including olive pulp extracts. Some common flavonoids identified in olive pulp extracts include

quercetin, apigenin, luteolin, and kaempferol. Both polyphenols and flavonoids have been extensively studied for their health-promoting effects, particularly their antioxidant activity, which protects cells from oxidative damage caused by free radicals. It is important to note that the composition and concentration of polyphenols and flavonoids in olive pulp extracts may vary depending on several factors, including the olive variety, degree of ripeness, growing and storage conditions, harvesting time, and extraction methods[11].

3.2. Antioxidant activity

3.2.1. Ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP test)

The results of the reducing power of the olive pulp extracts and the standard antioxidants (gallic acid and Vit C) are presented in figure 01.

Figure 1. Reducing power of olive pulp extracts and standard antioxidants (The values followed with different letters indicate significant differences by ANOVA post hoc LSD Tukey test $p < 0.05$. OPC: olive pulp from Chemlal variety ; OPS: Olive pulp from Sigoise variety)

The result of the antioxidant activity of the phenolic extracts of olive pulp, evaluated by the reducing assay, revealed that the tested extracts exhibited significant reducing capacity with EC_{50} values in the order of $1301 \pm 57.79 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for the Chemlal variety and $1468.99 \pm 0.94 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for the Sigoise variety. However, the reducing power of these extracts was much lower than that of the standard antioxidants, gallic acid ($EC_{50} = 21.33 \pm 0.56 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and vitamin C ($EC_{50} = 64.33 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). The decreasing order of reducing power was as follows: Gallic acid > Vitamin C > Chemlal olive pulp > Sigoise olive pulp. Our findings are consistent with those of previous studies. Benlarbi et al. [12] reported that phenolic extracts of olive pulp possess considerable reducing activity, while Nadour et al. [13] demonstrated that the reducing power of phenolic substances extracted from Chemlal olive pulp increased proportionally with their concentration.

A strong positive correlation was observed between total polyphenols content and the reducing power of the studied extracts, with correlation coefficients of $r = 0.998$ for Chemlal and $r = 0.993$ for Sigoise olive pulp. Similar results were reported by Benlarbi et al. [12], who found a strong positive correlation between total phenolic content and antioxidant capacity measured by the FRAP assay. In addition, our results indicated that the flavonoids content of olive pulp extracts also showed a very high positive correlation with reducing power ($r = 0.999$ for Chemlal and $r = 0.998$ for Sigoise olive pulp). These findings confirm that phenolic compounds and flavonoids are the main contributors to the antioxidant activity of olive pulp and may play an important role in the health-promoting effects of these fruits.

3.2.2. DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity

The results of the DPPH free radical scavenging activity of the tested extracts and standard antioxidants are illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2. DPPH free radical scavenging activity of the tested extracts and standard antioxidants. (The values followed by different letters indicate significant differences by ANOVA post hoc LSD Tukey test $p < 0.05$. OPC: Olive pulp from Chemlal variety; OPS: Olive pulp from Sigoise variety).

The results of the antiradical activity of the studied olive pulp extracts against the DPPH free radical showed that the tested extracts exhibited considerable antioxidant activity, with IC_{50} values of $158.1 \pm 2.57 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for the Chemlal variety and $174.11 \pm 2.2 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for the Sigoise variety. Similar to the reducing power assay, this antiradical activity was lower than that of the standard antioxidants, vitamin C and gallic acid, which displayed much stronger antioxidant activity with IC_{50} values of $7.24 \pm 0.20 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and $4.26 \pm 0.18 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. Therefore the antiradical activity was classified in the following descending order: Gallic acid > Vitamin C > Chemlal olive pulp > Sigoise olive pulp. The antiradical potential of olive pulp has also been reported in previous studies. Benlarbi et al. [12] demonstrated that olive pulp extracts exhibited radical scavenging activity against 2,2'-azino-bis-(3-ethylbenzthiazoline-6-sulfonic acid radical cation (ABTS \cdot^+), while Morello et al. [14] showed that phenolic compounds present in Arbequina olive pulp possessed significant radical scavenging activity when evaluated by the DPPH assay. A strong positive correlation was observed between total phenolic content and DPPH radical scavenging activity, with correlation coefficients of $r = 0.988$ for Chemlal and $r = 0.970$ for Sigoise olive pulp. Moreover, a significant correlation was also found between antiradical activity and total flavonoids content ($r = 0.996$ for Chemlal and $r = 0.813$ for Sigoise olive pulp), confirming that phenolic compounds and flavonoids play a key role in the antioxidant potential of olive pulp.

3.2.3. Hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity

In recent years, numerous methods have been used to evaluate the antioxidant activity of natural products. However, their hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity has not been extensively investigated. In the present study, the hydrogen peroxide scavenging capacity of phenolic extracts from olive pulp was evaluated, and the results are presented in the following figure:

Figure 3. Hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity of olive pulp extracts and standard antioxidants (The values followed by different letters indicate significant differences by ANOVA post hoc LSD Tukey test $p < 0.05$. OPC: Olive pulp from Chemlal variety; OPS: Olive pulp from Sigoise variety).

Our findings showed that olive pulp extracts possess strong hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity, with IC_{50} values of $117.32 \pm 2.36 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for the Chemlal variety and $493.29 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for the Sigoise variety. The Chemlal extract demonstrated greater H_2O_2 scavenging activity than vitamin C, which exhibited the lowest activity with an IC_{50} of $250.48 \pm 0.74 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Similar results were reported by Nadour et al. [13]. The classification of the scavenging activity in the decreasing order of strength is as follows: Gallic acid > Chemlal olive pulp > Vitamin C > Sigoise olive pulp. The hydrogen peroxide scavenging capacity of phenolic compounds is mainly due to their electron-donating properties. The number of hydroxyl groups on the aromatic ring, as well as the type of substituents in the ortho or para positions, are crucial structural factors influencing the antioxidant activity of polyphenols [13]. The obtained results indicated a strong positive correlation between H_2O_2 scavenging activity and total phenolic content, with high correlation coefficients ($r = 0.998$) for both Chemlal and Sigoise olive pulp. A positive correlation was also observed between scavenging activity and flavonoids content ($r = 0.975$ for Chemlal and $r = 0.813$ for Sigoise olive pulp). The antioxidant capacity of olive pulp is primarily attributed to the presence of bioactive compounds, including oleuropein, hydroxytyrosol, and tyrosol, which are well known for their strong antioxidant activity [15].

• **Oleuropein**; A major phenolic compound found in olives, including the pulp. It's a potent antioxidant known for its ability to scavenge free radicals and protect against oxidative stress.

• **Hydroxytyrosol**; Derived from oleuropein, is a potent antioxidant present in olive pulp. Its unique chemical structure, particularly the catechol group, allows it to effectively neutralize free radicals and even chelate metal ions involved in oxidative processes.

• **Tyrosol**; Although generally present at lower concentrations than oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol also contributes to the overall antioxidant activity of olive pulp.

The antioxidant effect of phenolic compounds in olive pulp is influenced by multiple factors, including olive variety, ripening stage, environmental conditions (temperature, sunlight, rainfall), soil type, and geographical origin, all of which affect the phenolic profile and antioxidant activity of olives [13].

3.3. Correlation between the antioxidant assays

The antioxidant activity obtained from the DPPH assay was consistent with that from the FRAP assay for the olive pulp extracts, with very high correlation coefficients ($r = 0.995$ for Chemlal and $r = 0.838$ for Sigoise olive pulp extracts). This indicates that the antioxidants present in olive pulp extracts are capable of both scavenging free radicals (DPPH•) and reducing oxidants (ferric ions). Our findings are in agreement with those reported by Benlarbi et al. [12] and Prior et al. [16]. A strong positive correlation was also observed between the FRAP assay and hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity of the tested extracts, with high coefficients of correlation $r = 0.999$ for Chemlal and $r = 0.995$ for Sigoise olive pulp extract. Furthermore, the results revealed a strong positive correlation between the DPPH assay and hydrogen peroxide scavenging capacity, with correlation coefficients of $r = 0.994$ for Chemlal and $r = 0.784$ for Sigoise olive pulp.

3.4. Protective effect against lipid peroxidation

The results of the protective effect of olive pulp extracts and standard antioxidants against lipid peroxidation are presented in the following figures:

Figure 4. Protective effect of olive oil extracts, gallic acid and ascorbic acid against lipid peroxidation expressed in (A) MDA $\mu\text{mol/g}$ of tissue, and (B) the percentage of peroxidation inhibition. (The values followed by different letters indicate significant differences by ANOVA post hoc LSD Tukey test $p < 0.05$. GA: Gallic acid; Vit C: Vitamin C; OPC: Olive pulp from Chemlal variety; OPS: Olive pulp from Sigoise variety).

The obtained results indicated that olive pulp extracts exert a protective effect against lipid peroxidation and significantly reduce MDA levels ($94.83 \pm 0.46 \mu\text{mol/g}$ tissue for Chemlal olive pulp extract and $125.62 \pm 2.80 \mu\text{mol/g}$ tissue for Sigoise olive pulp extract), compared to the positive control, which showed the highest MDA concentration ($350.62 \pm 0.88 \mu\text{mol/g}$ tissue). The tested extracts significantly inhibited lipid peroxidation, with inhibition percentages of $72.94 \pm 0.13\%$ for Chemlal olive pulp and $64.16 \pm 0.79\%$ for Sigoise olive pulp. However, this inhibitory effect was lower than that of the standard antioxidants gallic acid and vitamin C, which exhibited higher inhibitory potentials ($86.26 \pm 0.53\%$ for gallic acid and $81.16 \pm 0.26\%$ for vitamin C), as demonstrated by their lower MDA levels ($48.14 \pm 1.87 \mu\text{mol/g}$ for gallic acid and $66.02 \pm 0.93 \mu\text{mol/g}$ for vitamin C). The protective effect of olive pulp extracts may be attributed to their bioactive compounds, particularly hydroxytyrosol, oleuropein, and tyrosol, which exert antioxidant activity through radical scavenging, metal-chelating, and membrane-stabilizing mechanisms. According to the literature, Oleuropein has been reported to protect cellular membranes from lipid peroxidation by neutralizing reactive oxygen species and inhibiting the propagation of lipid radicals [11]. Similarly, Manna et al. [17] demonstrated that hydroxytyrosol effectively protected human erythrocytes against H_2O_2 -induced lipid peroxidation, largely through its potent free radical

scavenging capacity. Tyrosol, although less potent than hydroxytyrosol, also contributes to the overall antioxidant defense by scavenging reactive species and enhancing cellular resistance to oxidative damage.

Our results suggest that the olive pulp extracts may efficiently prevent the initiation of lipid peroxidation and protect human body against oxidative stress. Olive pulp has been reported to exhibit significant antioxidant activity, which is attributed to its high content of diverse bioactive compounds. The main antioxidants present in olive pulp include phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and vitamin E. These molecules play a crucial role in scavenging and neutralizing reactive free radicals, thereby protecting cells from oxidative damage. Olive pulp contains a variety of phenolic compounds, including hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol, and oleuropein. These compounds possess potent antioxidant properties and contribute significantly to the overall antioxidant activity of olive pulp. Hydroxytyrosol is among the most abundant phenolic compounds in olive pulp. It exhibits strong antioxidant activity and has been reported to protect against oxidative stress-related diseases, such as cardiovascular disorders and cancer [18]. Flavonoids such as apigenin, luteolin, and quercetin are also present in olive pulp, where they enhance its antioxidant capacity and contribute to health-promoting effects [14]. Olive pulp also contains vitamin E, mainly in the form of tocopherols and tocotrienols, which protect cell membranes from oxidative damage and help maintain overall cellular health. The combination of different antioxidants present in olive pulp often exerts a synergistic effect, whereby the overall antioxidant activity exceeds the sum of the individual components. This synergy enhances the protective potential of olive pulp against oxidative stress. The antioxidant activity of olive pulp contributes to its numerous health benefits. Regular consumption of olive pulp or olive products rich in antioxidants has been associated with a reduced risk of chronic diseases, such as cardiovascular disease, certain types of cancer, and neurodegenerative disorders. It's important to note that the specific antioxidant content and activity of olive pulp can vary depending on factors such as olive variety, ripeness, processing methods, and storage conditions. Nevertheless, olive pulp is generally recognized as a valuable source of antioxidants with significant health-promoting properties.

IV. CONCLUSION

The results of our study demonstrated that phenolic extracts from olive pulp are rich in bioactive compounds with notable antioxidant activity, highlighting their potential as a natural source of antioxidants for applications in the food and pharmaceutical industries. Further, investigations on Algerian olive cultivars would be valuable to confirm these results and improve the characterization of local olive varieties. Moreover, future research should focus on analyzing the phenolic fractions of olive pulp in order to isolate and purify the bioactive compounds potentially responsible for the observed antioxidant activity.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge the support of the Laboratory of Research on Local Animal Products, Ibn Khaldoun University, Algeria, and the DGRST of the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.F. Lesgards, P. Durand, M. Lassarre, P. Stocker, G. Lesgards, A. Lanteaume., M. Prost, M. Plehucher-Michel, Assessment of lifestyle effects on the overall antioxidant capacity of healthy subjects, *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 110(5), pp.479-87, 2002. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.02110479>.
- [2] K. B. Pandey and S.I. Rizvi, Plant polyphenols as dietary antioxidants in human health and diseases, *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*, 2(5), pp.270-8, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.4161/oxim.2.5.9498>.
- [3] Bouarroudj K., Temendjari A., Larbat R. "Quality, composition and antioxidant activity of Algerian wild olive (*Olea europaea* L. subsp. *Oleaster*), oil, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 83, pp. 484-491, 2016.

- [4] V.L. Singleton, R.Orthofer, R.M.Lamuella-Raventos,"Analysis of total phenols and other oxidation substrates and antioxidants by means of folin-ciocalteu reagent", *Methods inEnzymolgy*, 299: 152-178.1999.
- [5] D.C.Quettier, B.Gresseier, J.Vasseur, et al Phenolic compounds and antioxidant activities of buckwheat (*Fagopyrumesculentum*Moench) hulls and flour. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*72: 35-42,2000.
- [6] G.C.Yenand P.D Duh, Antioxidative properties of methanolic extracts from peanut hulls, *Journal of the American Oil Chemists' Society*,70,pp.383–386,1993.<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02552711>.
- [7] Y.Y.Tien,C.C.Ng, C.C.Chang, W.S.Tseng, S.Kotwal, Y.T.Shyu, Studies of the lactic-fermentation of sugar apple (*Annonasquamosa L.*) puree, *Journal of Food and Drug Analysis*, 13,pp.377-381. 2005.<https://doi.org/10.38212/2224-6614.2572>
- [8] S.Kumar, D.Kumar, N.Singh, B.D.Vasiashst.,*In vitro* free radicals scavenging and antioxidant activity of *Moringaoleiferapods*, *Journal of herbal medicine and toxicology*,1,pp. 17-22. 2007
- [9] S.Kumar, A. Mishra, A.K. Pandey,Antioxidant mediated protective effect of *Partheniumhysterophorus* against oxidative damage using in vitro model, *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 13,120.<http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-13-120>.2013.
- [10] V.Gupta andM. Sharma, Protective effect of *cinnamomumtejpata* on lipid peroxide formation in isolated rat liver homogenate,*CurrentResearch Journal of Biological Sciences.*, 2(4): 246-249. 2010.
- [11] F.Nicoli ,C.Negro, M.Vergine, A.Aprile, E .Nutricati, E .Sabella, A.Miceli,A. Luvisi, L De Bellis,Evaluation of Phytochemical and Antioxidant Properties of 15 Italian *Oleaeuropaea L.* Cultivar Leaves, *Molecules*, 24, 1998.<https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24101998>.2019.
- [12] F.Benlarbi, P. Stokerc , M. Yousfia, Investigation of antioxidant and antihemolytic activities of Algerian defatted olive fruits (*oleaeuropaeaL.*) at two ripening stages, *Mediterranean Journal of Nutrition and Metabolism*,11,pp. 217–233, DOI:10.3233/MNM-17187.2018.
- [13] M.Nadour, P.Michaud, F.Moulti-Mati,Antioxidant Activities of Polyphenols Extracted from Olive (*Oleaeuropaea*) of Chamlal Variety,*Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology*, 167,pp.1802–1810.2012.
- [14]J.R.Morello, S.Vuorela, M.P. Romero, M.J Motilva, M. Heinonen,Antioxidant Activity of Olive Pulp and Olive Oil Phenolic Compounds of the Arbequina Cultivar. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*,53, pp.2002-2008.2005.
- [15] K.L. Tuck, P.J. .Hayball.,I.Stupans, Structural characterization of the metabolites of hydroxytyrosol, the principal phenolic component in olive oil, in rats. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*,50, pp.2404–2409.2002.
- [16] R. Prior, X. Wu, K. Schaich, Standardized methods for the determination of antioxidant capacity and phenolics in foods and dietary supplements, *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 53(10),pp. 4290-302. Doi: 10.1021/jf0502698.2005.
- [17] C. Manna, P. Galletti, V. Cucciolla, G. Montedoro, V. Zappia, Olive oil hydroxytyrosol protects human erythrocytes against oxidative damages, *Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*, 10,pp. 159–165. 1999.
- [18]Y.O'Dowd, F.Driss, P.My-Chan Dang, C.Elhim,M.A.Gougerot-Pocidalo, C.Pasquier, J.El-Benna, Antioxidant effect of hydroxytyrosol, a polyphenol from olive oil: scavenging of hydrogen peroxide but

not superoxide anion produced by human neutrophils, *Biochemical Pharmacology*, 68, pp. 2003–2008.
doi:10.1016/j.bcp.2004.06.023.2004.